

Supplementary videos for “Modeling transient wave activity in snow avalanches over irregular and erodible terrain”

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Movie 1. Field avalanche happened at the Vallée de la Sionne test site on 3 February 2015.

Movie 2. Numerical simulation of the 2015 VdIS avalanche. The color in the video shows the flow velocity, and the colorbar can be found in Fig. 3 of the manuscript.

Movie 3. Roll-waves in the simulated avalanche, where the particles ahead of the wave are eroded and the particles at the wave tail are not deposited. The color in the video shows the flow velocity, and the colorbar can be found in Fig. 3 of the manuscript.

Movie 4. Erosion-deposition waves in the simulated avalanche, where the particles ahead of the wave are eroded and the particles at the wave tail are deposited. The color in the video shows the flow velocity, and the colorbar can be found in Fig. 3 of the manuscript.

Movie 5. Frontal ploughing in the simulated VdIS avalanche. The color in the video shows the flow velocity, and the colorbar can be found in Fig. 3 of the manuscript.